

Machine-driven experimentation for solving challenging consolidation problems

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Consolidation in composite manufacturing presents a serious challenge for defect mitigation, predicting dimensional tolerances, and optimization of composite morphology due to nonlinearity of all the flow and deformation processes involved in it.

The aim of this project is to develop a material testing system capable of designing loading programmes and distinguishing between dominant deformation mechanisms rather than imposing rigid framework of arbitrarily selected models. This system should be self-developing, adaptable and capable of capturing the main characteristics of the consolidation process by interrogating the material in the way it independently decides.

Importance of consolidation

Importance of consolidation in defect formation
Consolidation is influenced by resin flow modes

Examples of different flow modes in the specimen. [1] Belnoue et al.

Cross section of samples showing the defects found [2] Hubert et al.

Characterisation testing strategies for different materials

No universal testing procedure for compaction of composite precursors

Low viscosity UD preregs

[2] Hubert et al.

Impregnated mat for liquid moulding

[3] Kelly et al.

Toughened preregs

[1] Belnoue et al.

Project scheme

Based on the hardware's output Processing framework produces adaptable loading schedule for the current timestep of the process

Consolidation sensor is capable of recognizing the flow/deformation modes by its characteristic signatures

